

1 **Table S1.** Calculated unit-cell volumes and full C_{ij} 's of $\text{Si}_{15}\text{H}_4\text{O}_{32}$ with the hydrogarnet
 2 water substitution and dry SiO_2 stishovite at high pressure

Pressure (GPa)	Volume ($\text{\AA}^3$)	C_{11} (GPa)	C_{12} (GPa)	C_{13} (GPa)	C_{33} (GPa)	C_{44} (GPa)	C_{66} (GPa)
$\text{Si}_{15}\text{H}_4\text{O}_{32}$							
0	45.96	409.5	180.2	170.7	692.0	235.1	275.5
1	45.79	415.8	186.9	173.5	697.8	237.4	278.8
2	45.63	421.9	193.5	176.3	703.5	239.7	282.2
3	45.47	427.8	200.1	179.1	709.1	242.0	285.4
4	45.31	433.8	206.8	181.9	714.8	244.3	288.6
5	45.16	439.5	213.3	184.7	720.4	246.5	291.9
6	45.00	445.2	219.9	187.5	726.0	248.7	295.0
7	44.86	450.6	226.5	190.3	731.6	250.9	298.2
8	44.71	456.0	233.1	193.0	737.1	253.0	301.3
9	44.57	461.3	239.6	195.7	742.6	255.2	304.3
10	44.43	466.3	246.2	198.4	748.0	257.3	307.3
dry SiO_2							
0	45.38	449.1	212.9	190.4	743.8	256.1	324.0
1	45.24	454.8	220.0	193.7	751.1	258.2	327.6
2	45.09	460.5	226.9	196.0	756.1	260.3	331.1
3	44.95	465.7	234.1	198.6	761.8	262.3	334.6
4	44.81	471.3	240.7	201.0	767.1	264.4	338.0
5	44.67	476.5	247.4	203.4	772.3	266.3	341.4
6	44.54	481.5	253.7	205.9	777.4	268.3	344.7
7	44.40	486.5	260.5	208.4	782.7	270.3	348.0
8	44.27	491.5	267.5	210.8	788.1	272.3	351.4
9	44.14	496.1	274.1	213.4	793.6	274.2	354.7
10	44.02	500.5	281.0	215.7	798.6	276.1	357.9

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7 **Table S2.** C_{ij0} and C_{ij0}' of dry SiO_2 and $\text{Si}_{15}\text{O}_{32}\text{H}_4$ stishovite. LDA: local density
8 approximation in *ab initio* calculations; BLS: Brillouin light scattering; ISLS: Impulsive
9 simulated light scattering.

Composition	$\text{Si}_{15}\text{O}_{32}\text{H}_4$	SiO_2	SiO_2	SiO_2	SiO_2
Reference	This study	This study	Zhang et al., (2021)	Jiang et al., (2009)	Yang and Wu, (2014)
Method	LDA, static	LDA, static	BLS + ISLS, 300K	BLS, 300 K	LDA, static
V_0	45.96	45.38	46.57(3)	46.40(2)	46.32
C_{110}	409.5	449.1	454(2)	452.2	452.3
C_{120}	180.2	212.9	196(3)	199.8	229.6
C_{130}	170.7	190.4	193(3)	191.3	189.7
C_{330}	692.0	743.8	760(7)	761.0	743.2
C_{440}	235.1	256.1	262(2)	256.7	252.0
C_{660}	275.5	324.0	320(2)	320.3	329.0
C_{110}'	5.72(1)	5.23(2)	4.62(4)	4.8(3)	4.41(5)
C_{120}'	6.38(1)	6.63(2)	6.51(5)	6.3(3)	6.53(5)
C_{130}'	2.73(1)	2.53(2)	1.66(11)	1.7(3)	2.41(5)
C_{330}'	5.64(1)	5.59(2)	4.02(16)	5.7(3)	5.61(5)
C_{440}'	2.23(1)	2.02(2)	1.80(3)	2.0(3)	1.89(5)
C_{660}'	3.18(1)	3.39(2)	3.16(3)	2.2(3)	3.19(5)

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22 **Table S3.** Effects of the hydrogarnet substitution on C_{ij0} and C_{ij0}' . A Linear function was
 23 used to fit C_{ij0} and C_{ij0}' of dry SiO_2 and $\text{Si}_{15}\text{O}_{32}\text{H}_4$ stishovite, C_{ij0} (or C_{ij0}') = $k \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (in
 24 wt%) + $C_{ij0,dry}$ (or $C_{ij0,dry}'$).

	C_{110}	C_{120}	C_{130}	C_{330}	C_{440}	C_{660}
k	-10.30	-8.51	-5.12	-13.48	-5.46	-12.62
$C_{ij0,dry}$	449.1	212.9	190.4	743.8	256.1	324.0
	C_{110}'	C_{120}'	C_{130}'	C_{330}'	C_{440}'	C_{660}'
k	0.1275	-0.0650	0.0520	0.0130	0.0546	-0.0546
$C_{ij0,dry}'$	5.23	6.63	2.53	5.59	2.02	3.39

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57 **Table S4.** Landau parameters of $\text{Si}_{0.95}\text{H}_{0.21}\text{O}_2$ across the post-stishovite transition. Those
 58 for dry SiO_2 are also listed for comparison.

Compositions	$\text{Si}_{0.95}\text{H}_{0.21}\text{O}_2$	SiO_2
		0.004 mol% H^+
References	This study	Zhang et al. (2021)
P_C^* , GPa	28	55.0(10)
$(P_C - P_C^*)$, GPa	87	55.2(10)
a	-0.03784(35)	-0.0501(29)
b , GPa	11	11
λ_1 , GPa	6.7(14)	11.03(85)
λ_2 , GPa	37.2	27.61
λ_3 , GPa	19.0(15)	16.79(92)
λ_4 , GPa	18.94	18.94(31)
λ_6 , GPa	15.15	15.15(22)
C_{110}^0 , GPa	733.9	592.3
$C_{11}^{0'}$	6.03	10.80(47)
C_{120}^0 , GPa	-132.1	57.9
$C_{12}^{0'}$	6.03	8.81(63)
C_{130}^0 , GPa	174.0	193.0
$C_{13}^{0'}$	2.70	2.91(27)
C_{330}^0 , GPa	700.7	760.2
$C_{33}^{0'}$	5.63	7.07(48)
C_{440}^0 , GPa	238.6	261.6
$C_{44}^{0'}$	2.19	3.18(5)
C_{660}^0 , GPa	283.6	319.7
$C_{66}^{0'}$	3.22	5.60(13)

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67**Table S5.** Modeled full C_{ij} 's of $\text{Si}_{15}\text{O}_{32}\text{H}_4$ across the post-stishovite transition at high pressure and 300 K (St: stishovite; Pst: post-stishovite)

P (GPa)	Phase	C_{11} (GPa)	C_{12} (GPa)	C_{13} (GPa)	C_{22} (GPa)	C_{23} (GPa)	C_{33} (GPa)	C_{44} (GPa)	C_{55} (GPa)	C_{66} (GPa)
0	St	416.1	185.7	174.0			700.7	238.6		283.6
1	St	421.8	197.0	177.8			708.5	241.7		288.1
2	St	426.9	208.0	181.4			716.0	244.6		292.4
3	St	431.6	218.8	184.9			723.1	247.4		296.5
4	St	436.0	229.5	188.2			729.9	250.0		300.5
5	St	440.0	240.0	191.4			736.4	252.6		304.2
6	St	443.6	250.3	194.5			742.6	255.1		307.9
7	St	447.0	260.6	197.5			748.7	257.4		311.4
8	St	450.1	270.7	200.4			754.5	259.7		314.9
9	St	452.9	280.8	203.3			760.1	262.0		318.2
10	St	455.5	290.8	206.1			765.6	264.1		321.5
11	St	457.9	300.8	208.8			770.9	266.3		324.7
12	St	460.1	310.7	211.5			776.1	268.3		327.8
13	St	462.0	320.6	214.1			781.2	270.3		330.8
14	St	463.8	330.4	216.6			786.1	272.3		333.8
15	St	465.4	340.3	219.1			790.9	274.2		336.7
16	St	466.8	350.1	221.6			795.6	276.1		339.5
17	St	468.0	360.0	224.0			800.3	278.0		342.3
18	St	469.0	369.8	226.4			804.8	279.8		345.1
19	St	469.8	379.7	228.7			809.2	281.5		347.8
20	St	470.5	389.5	231.0			813.6	283.3		350.4
21	St	471.0	399.4	233.3			817.8	285.0		353.1
22	St	471.3	409.4	235.5			822.0	286.7		355.6
23	St	471.5	419.3	237.7			826.1	288.3		358.2
24	St	471.5	429.3	239.9			830.2	290.0		360.7
25	St	471.4	439.4	242.1			834.2	291.6		363.2
26	St	471.0	449.5	244.2			838.1	293.2		365.6
27	St	470.5	459.6	246.3			841.9	294.7		368.0
27.5	St	470.2	464.7	247.3			843.9	295.5		369.2
27.9	St	469.9	468.8	248.2			845.4	296.1		370.1
28	St	469.9	469.9	248.4			845.8	296.3		370.4
28.1	Pst	465.4	469.3	240.2	477.2	256.8	846.0	297.2	295.7	370.6
28.5	Pst	464.0	467.3	230.8	490.0	267.4	846.8	298.7	295.4	371.6
29	Pst	465.8	464.9	224.2	502.1	275.5	847.9	300.1	295.5	372.8
30	Pst	472.4	460.3	216.0	522.5	286.7	850.1	302.6	296.0	375.3
31	Pst	480.5	456.2	210.5	540.5	295.1	852.3	304.8	296.8	377.7
32	Pst	489.2	452.5	206.6	556.9	302.1	854.5	306.9	297.6	380.1
33	Pst	498.2	449.1	203.6	572.2	308.0	856.7	308.9	298.5	382.4
34	Pst	507.2	446.1	201.4	586.5	313.2	859.0	310.8	299.5	384.7
35	Pst	516.3	443.4	199.7	600.1	317.9	861.2	312.6	300.4	387.1

36	Pst	525.3	441.0	198.5	613.0	322.2	863.5	314.5	301.4	389.3
37	Pst	534.2	438.9	197.6	625.3	326.1	865.7	316.2	302.4	391.6
38	Pst	543.0	437.0	196.9	637.1	329.7	868.0	318.0	303.4	393.8
39	Pst	551.6	435.4	196.6	648.5	333.1	870.3	319.7	304.4	396.1
40	Pst	560.2	434.0	196.4	659.3	336.3	872.6	321.4	305.4	398.3
41	Pst	568.5	432.9	196.4	669.8	339.2	874.8	323.0	306.4	400.5
42	Pst	576.8	431.9	196.6	679.9	342.1	877.1	324.6	307.4	402.6
43	Pst	584.9	431.1	196.9	689.7	344.7	879.4	326.2	308.4	404.8
44	Pst	592.8	430.5	197.3	699.2	347.3	881.7	327.8	309.4	406.9
45	Pst	600.6	430.1	197.8	708.3	349.7	884.0	329.4	310.3	409.0
46	Pst	608.3	429.8	198.4	717.2	352.1	886.3	330.9	311.3	411.1
47	Pst	615.8	429.7	199.2	725.8	354.3	888.5	332.4	312.3	413.2
48	Pst	623.2	429.8	199.9	734.2	356.5	890.8	333.9	313.3	415.3
49	Pst	630.4	429.9	200.8	742.3	358.6	893.1	335.4	314.3	417.3
50	Pst	637.5	430.2	201.7	750.2	360.6	895.3	336.9	315.2	419.4
51	Pst	644.5	430.6	202.7	757.9	362.6	897.6	338.3	316.2	421.4
52	Pst	651.4	431.1	203.7	765.4	364.5	899.8	339.8	317.2	423.4
53	Pst	658.2	431.8	204.7	772.8	366.3	902.1	341.2	318.1	425.4
54	Pst	664.8	432.5	205.8	779.9	368.1	904.3	342.6	319.1	427.4
55	Pst	671.4	433.4	206.9	786.9	369.9	906.6	344.0	320.0	429.3
56	Pst	677.8	434.3	208.1	793.7	371.6	908.8	345.4	321.0	431.3
57	Pst	684.1	435.3	209.3	800.4	373.3	911.0	346.7	321.9	433.2
58	Pst	690.3	436.4	210.5	806.9	375.0	913.2	348.1	322.9	435.2
59	Pst	696.5	437.6	211.8	813.3	376.6	915.4	349.4	323.8	437.1
60	Pst	702.5	438.9	213.0	819.6	378.2	917.6	350.8	324.7	439.0
61	Pst	708.4	440.2	214.3	825.7	379.7	919.8	352.1	325.6	440.9
62	Pst	714.2	441.6	215.6	831.7	381.3	922.0	353.4	326.5	442.8
63	Pst	720.0	443.1	216.9	837.6	382.8	924.2	354.7	327.5	444.7
64	Pst	725.7	444.6	218.3	843.4	384.3	926.4	356.0	328.4	446.5
65	Pst	731.3	446.2	219.6	849.1	385.7	928.5	357.3	329.3	448.4
66	Pst	736.8	447.9	221.0	854.6	387.2	930.7	358.5	330.2	450.2
67	Pst	742.2	449.6	222.4	860.1	388.6	932.8	359.8	331.0	452.1
68	Pst	747.6	451.4	223.7	865.5	390.0	935.0	361.0	331.9	453.9
69	Pst	752.8	453.2	225.1	870.7	391.4	937.1	362.3	332.8	455.7
70	Pst	758.0	455.1	226.5	875.9	392.8	939.2	363.5	333.7	457.5
71	Pst	763.2	457.0	227.9	881.0	394.1	941.3	364.7	334.6	459.3
72	Pst	768.3	459.0	229.3	886.1	395.5	943.5	366.0	335.4	461.1
73	Pst	773.3	461.0	230.8	891.0	396.8	945.6	367.2	336.3	462.9
74	Pst	778.2	463.0	232.2	895.9	398.1	947.7	368.4	337.2	464.7
75	Pst	783.1	465.1	233.6	900.7	399.4	949.7	369.6	338.0	466.4
76	Pst	787.9	467.2	235.0	905.4	400.7	951.8	370.7	338.9	468.2
77	Pst	792.7	469.4	236.5	910.1	402.0	953.9	371.9	339.7	469.9
78	Pst	797.4	471.6	237.9	914.6	403.3	955.9	373.1	340.6	471.7
79	Pst	802.0	473.8	239.3	919.2	404.6	958.0	374.2	341.4	473.4
80	Pst	806.6	476.1	240.8	923.6	405.8	960.0	375.4	342.2	475.1

81	Pst	811.1	478.4	242.2	928.0	407.1	962.1	376.5	343.1	476.8
82	Pst	815.6	480.7	243.7	932.4	408.3	964.1	377.7	343.9	478.5
83	Pst	820.1	483.1	245.1	936.6	409.5	966.1	378.8	344.7	480.2
84	Pst	824.4	485.5	246.5	940.9	410.7	968.2	379.9	345.5	481.9
85	Pst	828.8	487.9	248.0	945.0	411.9	970.2	381.1	346.4	483.6
86	Pst	833.1	490.3	249.4	949.1	413.1	972.2	382.2	347.2	485.3
87	Pst	837.3	492.8	250.9	953.2	414.3	974.2	383.3	348.0	486.9
88	Pst	841.5	495.3	252.3	957.2	415.5	976.1	384.4	348.8	488.6
89	Pst	845.7	497.8	253.8	961.2	416.7	978.1	385.5	349.6	490.3
90	Pst	849.8	500.3	255.2	965.1	417.9	980.1	386.6	350.4	491.9
91	Pst	853.8	502.9	256.6	969.0	419.0	982.1	387.6	351.2	493.6
92	Pst	857.9	505.5	258.1	972.8	420.2	984.0	388.7	352.0	495.2
93	Pst	861.9	508.1	259.5	976.6	421.4	986.0	389.8	352.8	496.8
94	Pst	865.8	510.7	261.0	980.4	422.5	987.9	390.9	353.5	498.4
95	Pst	869.7	513.3	262.4	984.1	423.7	989.8	391.9	354.3	500.1
96	Pst	873.6	516.0	263.8	987.7	424.8	991.8	393.0	355.1	501.7
97	Pst	877.4	518.7	265.3	991.4	425.9	993.7	394.0	355.9	503.3
98	Pst	881.2	521.3	266.7	995.0	427.1	995.6	395.1	356.7	504.9
99	Pst	885.0	524.1	268.1	998.5	428.2	997.5	396.1	357.4	506.5
100	Pst	888.7	526.8	269.5	1002.0	429.3	999.4	397.1	358.2	508.1

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91 **Table S6.** K , G , ρ , V_S , and V_P of $\text{Si}_{15}\text{O}_{32}\text{H}_4$ across the post-stishovite transition at high
 92 pressure and 300 K (St: stishovite; Pst: post-stishovite)

P (GPa)	Phase	K_S (GPa)	G (GPa)	ρ (g/cm ³)	V_S (km/s)	V_P (km/s)
0	St	282.4	207.7	4.135	7.09	11.63
2	St	292.5	208.9	4.167	7.08	11.71
4	St	302.6	209.7	4.198	7.07	11.78
6	St	312.5	210.2	4.228	7.05	11.84
8	St	322.4	210.1	4.258	7.02	11.90
10	St	332.3	209.4	4.287	6.99	11.94
12	St	342.0	207.9	4.315	6.94	11.98
14	St	351.7	205.3	4.342	6.88	12.00
16	St	361.4	201.3	4.369	6.79	12.01
18	St	371.0	195.4	4.396	6.67	11.99
20	St	380.5	187.0	4.421	6.50	11.94
22	St	390.0	175.5	4.447	6.28	11.85
24	St	399.4	160.2	4.472	5.98	11.71
26	St	408.8	140.9	4.496	5.60	11.52
28	St	417.7	125.8	4.519	5.28	11.38
30	St + Pst	423.8	144.0	4.536	5.63	11.65
32	St + Pst	429.0	161.9	4.553	5.96	11.90
34	St + Pst	433.3	179.7	4.571	6.27	12.13
36	St + Pst	437.0	197.4	4.588	6.56	12.35
38	St + Pst	440.1	215.3	4.606	6.84	12.56
40	St + Pst	442.5	233.5	4.624	7.11	12.77
42	Pst	444.4	252.3	4.642	7.37	12.97
44	Pst	449.9	259.5	4.663	7.46	13.06
46	Pst	455.4	265.8	4.684	7.53	13.15
48	Pst	460.9	271.4	4.704	7.60	13.23
50	Pst	466.3	276.5	4.724	7.65	13.29
52	Pst	471.6	281.1	4.744	7.70	13.36
54	Pst	477.0	285.5	4.763	7.74	13.42
56	Pst	482.2	289.5	4.783	7.78	13.47
58	Pst	487.5	293.4	4.802	7.82	13.53
60	Pst	492.7	297.1	4.821	7.85	13.58
62	Pst	497.8	300.6	4.840	7.88	13.63
64	Pst	503.0	304.1	4.859	7.91	13.67
66	Pst	508.0	307.4	4.877	7.94	13.72
68	Pst	513.1	310.6	4.895	7.97	13.76
70	Pst	518.1	313.8	4.913	7.99	13.81

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97 **Table S7.** Thermoelastic parameters of MORB components from this study, Gréaux et al.
 98 (2019), Stixrude & Lithgow-Bertelloni (2022), and Fu et al. (2023)

MORB components	V_0 (cm ³ /mol)	K_0 (GPa)	K'_0	G_0 (GPa)	G'_0	θ_0	γ_0	q_0	η_{so}
Si _{0.95} H _{0.21} O ₂ stishovite	14.20	282.6	4.60	215.8	1.07	1092	1.56	2.2	4.4
Si _{0.95} H _{0.21} O ₂ post-stishovite	14.22	314.0	3.18	200.2	1.86	1092	1.56	2.2	4.4
Si _{0.98} H _{0.10} O ₂ stishovite	14.11	295.8	4.18	225.1	1.00	1092	1.56	2.2	4.4
Si _{0.98} H _{0.10} O ₂ post-stishovite	14.07	316.5	3.24	188.3	2.02	1092	1.56	2.2	4.4
bridgmanite	24.61	235.3	4.42	174	1.83	900	1.57	1.1	2.4
Ca-perovskite	27.33	248	4.0	126	1.6	1000	1.42	2.65	1.54
CaFe ₂ O ₄ -type phase	36.18	211	4.1	130	1.8	863	1.31	1.0	2.1
MgO	11.26	159.5	4.0	129	2.32	760	1.4	1.2	2.6

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